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ENGLISH ARCHEOLOGY

Abstract: *ENGLISH ARCHEOLOGY??? What is it? First of all, I explain the word "ARCHEOLOGY". It is known that archaeologists organize expeditions in different places and look for ancient artifacts there. They polish the found objects and make them into a finished exhibit. Therefore, English archaeology means enhancing teaching methods that are now considered obsolete and boring into "new exhibits".*

Key words: *English archeology, new exhibits, suggestopedia*

Introduction.

The word "classroom" refers to the environment in which a teacher stands in front of a class of 30 to 40 students and gives a lecture with a specific weight of his or her voice. In addition, every day our teacher served up the same menu: Memorizing verbs, answering worksheets, taking dictation and repeating, repeating, repeating. These are common teaching methods when we were in school. However, over the years, things have changed, and while these have been one of the most effective ways to teach English to young students, they have not changed. This can be for a variety of reasons, probably:

- the current generation gets to know the world through social media
- their knowledge base is filled with information available on the internet
- Nowadays, students are more impatient and teaching methods need to be adapted to their dynamic thinking process in order to attract their attention.

Language teaching has its challenges. Most of the time, a learner can't pick up from his/her surroundings because, we do not have atmosphere. In this case, teacher should teach patiently and systematically, it means the teacher has to better engage the students with new methods and games, which will be needed to improve the quality of learning. In this article, it will be discussed methods and games that are useful for teachers while teaching English in classes.

"NEW EXHIBITS" IN ENGLISH

According to Asher and James (1982), "Methods are the combination of techniques that are used and plasticized by the teachers in the classrooms to teach their students and approaches are the philosophies of teachers about language teaching that can be applied in the classrooms by using different techniques of language teaching."

We know that to learn any language, first of all, we need grammar to make sentences, but sometimes we make some grammatical mistakes. Fortunately, we have one method that is called **SUGGESTOPEDIA**, which is based on memorization of language “chunks.” For example, students read dialogues and texts aloud, usually to the rhythm of some type of music. The music is generally classical music, or some other genre suitable to target structure. This is known as “concert reading”.

The use of concert reading fosters a comfortable learning environment, particularly for those students who feel shy and apprehensive. The Suggestopedia method is suitable for all levels and allows for lots of creativity and fun. Even advanced students can get a kick out of “singing” through their dialogues. For example, if the focus of the lesson is prepositions, you can sing out the following sentence: “*Joe went ___ the supermarket ___ the street.*” Then, students will shout back, “*to*” and “*across*” to fill in the blanks.

This type of reading makes for a great controlled practice following a grammar presentation.

In addition, after grammar lessons in the classroom, the organization of specific games on particular topic makes it easier to remember. For instance, teacher teaches the topic of the **present perfect tense** in the classroom, and at the end of the lesson he hands out a piece of paper with the words **I have ever** on one side and **I have never** on the other side. After that, the teacher asks them various questions and the students respond them by showing short answers in the paper:

— Have you ever gone to Paris?

— I have ever/ I have never.

According to many students, another challenge in the process of learning English is the lack of vocabulary and the difficulty of remembering words. Usually, we simply memorize words by translating them from our native language into English, but it can make the process more fun and easier to remember through a variety of activities. For example, new theme is **ADJECTIVES**. Firstly, students will learn definitions of new words related to a new topic.

ADORABLE - extremely charming or appealing;

BRIGHT - radiating or reflecting light;

INTELLIGENT - having or indicating a high or satisfactory degree of intelligence and mental capacity; and etc.

After that, they play a game familiar to them from their youth.

adorable	bright	intelligent
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delicious	serious	quiet
angry	stupid	talkative

Students are divided into small groups of two and play this game. The first student composes a sentence from words what he/she wants and draws an "X". The next participant also composes a sentence and draws an "O". By organizing this game in the classroom, we will also get rid of the boring word memorization method, the words will be remembered faster than before, and the lesson will be interesting for all students at the same time.

Not only this, we can speed up the memorization of words by teaching mnemonics, which is becoming increasingly popular today. In mnemonics, the first task in memorizing a new word is to find an image for the word, then learn by heart this image along with the original meaning of the word. As an example I should say the word "RANGE". The original meaning of this word is "a series of things in a line" and I can say as an image for this word is "RANGE ROVER" CARS. Now, we should connect both of them together: "Range Rover car series". with the help of this strategy we can remember words easily and these will be sealed in our mind for a lifetime.

IN CONCLUSION

Teachers are the torchbearers of a civilized society. For ages, teachers have used different methods, approaches, and styles to suit the child's requirements. Teaching English as a second language is a challenge as we can see that for non-native speakers, various methods need to be devised. So teachers of this century will put together all the methods to find the best one.

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